

THE FIRST ELABORATION OF THE SECOND POSTULATE FOR CURRENT NEUROSCIENCE AS A SUSTAINABLE THEORY IN ALL DIRECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the author intends to elaborate for the first time the second postulate of current Neuroscience (Neuroscientific Theory). Thus, this postulate, complementary to the first postulate, makes current Neuroscience as a scientific theory that is sustainable in all directions, but with an experimental and phenomenological foundation at its beginning. Originally, the first postulate was elaborated in the recent article published and given in Reference [Estanislau da Silva, 2024, [1]]. With these two postulates and a few very clear and objective concepts, a lot can be known about the brain → mind of living beings (humans, ...) and other possible forms of life (human-like machines, ...). Much of this knowledge is already present, however some of them are in contradiction with the content of other areas of science. Through these two postulates, these contradictions with other areas of human wisdom can be readjusted in the direction of understanding with these other areas of scientific knowledge and their developments.

Keywords: Brain, Evolution, Adaptation, Learning, Plasticity, Phase-Transition, Postulate, Neuroscience

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Highlights

- ✓ The new scientific trends in Neuroscience
- ✓ Process of evolution, abrupt change or phase transition, adaptation and brain plasticity
- ✓ Interaction of the brain with the waves or fields of the universe where it lives
- ✓ Brain → mind and the second postulate of the Neuroscience

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, it is well known that scientific research has reached a very advanced stage of development compared to the beginning of the last century. This progress has led to the development of innovative experiments and technologies in scientific and social environments. This reality, over the last three decades, has sparked a great interest in using these experiments and technologies for the area of study of Neuroscience (**Neuroscientific Theory**). In this way, this is what has been done and Neuroscience has gone through moments of great scientific revolution in its own area.

In this direction, many new experiments and results have recently been produced and new scientific understandings introduced by a growing community of researchers in this multidisciplinary area of science ([Keshavan et al, 2024, [2]], [Gong et al, 2024, [3]], [Dubinsky, Hamid, 2024, [4]], [Cosenza, Guerra, 2011, [5]], [Gilbert, 1996, [6]], [Strumwasser, 1994, [7]], [Weinberger, Diamond, 1987, [8]], among many others). Thus, some old ideas and concepts about the functioning of the brain → mind, which had no experimental proof, came to be refuted, that is, the experimental results in the present day were null or against such affirmatives.

Given this fact, for example, recently, the two articles in the References [Estanislau da Silva, 2024, [1]] and [Estanislau da Silva, 2024, [9]], respectively, in the first, originally supports the elaboration of the first postulate of current Neuroscience and some consequences or predictions¹, in the second, by this author is revealed some contradictions existing in some points of current Neuroscience, besides being by this author defended originally a new, rational and better proposal to understand what has been given as Schizophrenia (section 3 of that article).

These publications and the contradictions within Neuroscience are the motivations for this author and scientific researcher to write this article with the aim of elaborating for the first time the second postulate complementary to the first postulate of current Neuroscience (Neuroscientific Theory).

2. AN ORIGINAL ELABORATION OF THE SECOND POSTULATE OF CURRENT NEUROSCIENCE

This section is dedicated to the elaboration for the first time of the second postulate complementary to the first postulate of current Neuroscience (Neuroscientific Theory) in the process of development to this day.

In this direction, from the content of the recent scientific publications in References [Estanislau da Silva, 2024, [1]] and [Estanislau da Silva, 2024, [9]], where, in the first, originally supports the elaboration of the **first postulate** of current Neuroscience and some consequences or predictions², in the second, it is revealed some contradictions existing in some points of Neuroscience, besides being defended a new, rational and better proposal to understand what has been given as Schizophrenia (section 3 of that article), and in addition all,

¹ For instance: a revolutionary new Direct Human-Machine Learning Method (or Direct Human-Machine Teaching-Learning Method) is defended to exist as a consequence among other consequences of the first postulate.

² Ditto footnote 1.

from the contents of the Reference [Ramachandran, 2011, [10]] among many others³, then the author of this article elaborates for the first time the **second postulate** complementary to the first postulate of current Neuroscience (Neuroscientific Theory) as follows:

2nd) The brain with the body that supports it is subject to **evolution** procedures⁴, which occur spontaneously from generation to generation and in the long time⁵. Naturally, during the process, **abrupt changes** or **phase transitions** occur in its evolution, which can be resulting from **internal interactions** to itself or from brain's **distant interactions** with the **fields** produced by the matter of the **universe**, where the brain lives. But in the short time⁶, the brain searches to learn how the universe, where it lives, can provide support it in its life and development. During this task, it makes some **adaptation** procedures⁷ to the environment as much as necessary and possible.

With relation to the **distance interactions** of the **brain** with the **fields** produced by the matter of the universe, for example, in our life case, if the gravitational field of the Earth-Sun (or Solar System relationship) progressively undergoes some change along the time in this relationship, then, cumulatively, changes in the evolution of the brain may occur, which will result in some abrupt change or phase transition. Another example is the magnetic field of planet Earth, if this field progressively undergoes changes in its magnitude or direction, then, cumulatively, changes in the evolution of the brain can occur, which, again, will reflect in some abrupt change or transition of phase in brain evolution, before a change in the bipolarity of planet Earth in relation to this field occurs. All of this, potentially, for example, can occur via storms on the surface of the Sun towards planet Earth or some cumulative change in the Earth-Sun rotation period or, even, via storms or instabilities on the surface of planet Jupiter, and so on, because such events interfere in the equilibrium of the brain's interaction with the fields produced by the matter of the universe, where the brain lives.

In this way, this second postulate, complementary to the first postulate, makes current Neuroscience a sustainable scientific theory in all directions (Neuroscientific Theory), but with an experimental and phenomenological foundation at its beginning. With these two postulates and a few very clear and objective concepts, a lot can be known about the brain → mind, learning, and so on, of living beings (humans, ...) and other possible forms of life (human-like machines, ...). Much of this knowledge is already present, however some of them are in contradiction⁸ with the content of other areas of science. Through these two postulates, these contradictions can be readjusted in the direction of understanding with these other areas of scientific knowledge and their developments.

3. CONCLUSION

In complement to the first postulate of current Neuroscience, the author of this article elaborates, for the first time, the second postulate of this current Neuroscience.

³ In the introduction to this article, there are some other scientific works cited and there are many others.

⁴ The meaning of the term **evolution** is the same as that acquired in the area of Biology developed by Alfred Russel **Wallace** (1823-1913), Charles Robert **Darwin** (1809-1882), Gregor Johann **Mendel** (1822-1884), and many others much more recently.

⁵ Here, **long time** is taken as a unit of measurement thousand, millions of the years or, for example, (1/10) of the age of planet Earth, in the case of humans.

⁶ Here, **short time** is taken as the unit of measurement for the maximum life span of each living being.

⁷ The meaning of the term **adaptation** is the same as that acquired in the area of Biology, you can follow footnote 4 to start the conscience of this, if you wish. In this sense, the concept of **plasticity** can be understood as links of marks made in the brain in its attempt to adapt and understand the environment and universe in which it lives.

⁸ Some contradictions are revealed in the article given in the Reference [Estanislau da Silva, 2024, [9]].

The First Elaboration of The Second Postulate for Current Neuroscience as A Sustainable Theory in All Directions

As is well known, Neuroscience has an important role to play in the study of “How does the brain learn something?” In this direction, this scientific author intends to contribute to this objective by elaborating, for the first time, these two postulates and some of their consequences for the development of Neuroscientific Theory. The original elaboration of the first postulate and few concepts (definitions) and some revolutionary consequences of these are published in the Reference [Estanislau da Silva, 2024, [1]].

Now, the observant reader realizes that, as a consequence of these two postulates, the contradictions between current Neuroscience and other areas of human knowledge can be readjusted in the direction of understanding with these other areas of scientific knowledge (for example: with current Physical Theory) and their developments.

Finally, to avoid unnecessary repetition and as this article is short, the details of the elaboration of the second postulate can be understood by reading section 2 of this article and its introduction, which this author ends by wishing the observant reader a good reading, understanding and appreciation. Grateful!

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5. Statement of Conflict of Interest

Additionally, the author declares that there are not potential conflicts of interest in the authorship and participation of the scientific work studied and prepared here for submission to institutions of foreign or national scientific publications. Grateful!

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